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PACE – PEDAGOGY FOR ACADEMIC COLLEGE ENGINEERING - NEW VARIANTS ON HYBRID LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Education methodology is a constantly developing field. From kindergarten to academy new methods and approaches are suggested almost daily. Many of the methods are excellent for some age ranges but have no advantage for others. In this paper we scan through the main pedagogies used in the academy for engineering education and focus on the advantages and disadvantages of the flipped classroom. Next, we target the asymmetry problem of the Flipped Classroom and suggest several novelties we call PACE (Pedagogy for Academic College Engineering). First, we suggest a periodic approach for teaching (the Sine-wave approach), we will show that this approach corrects the main problem of the Flipped Classroom but might be over-symmetric. Next, we suggest an improvement in a new non-symmetric approach (the Sinc-function approach). Finally, the previous learning method portrayed by an even function will be replaced by an approach portrayed by an odd function (the signed-Sinc approach). While the Sine-wave approach allows perfect symmetry between on-campus and off campus activities (or between lecturer responsibilities and students responsibilities), the Sinc-function approach requires more time on-campus and more responsibility falls in the lap of the lecturer. The signed-Sinc approach regains the temporal symmetry between on-campus and off-campus activity by generating asymmetry between pre-lecture and post-lecture activities. All these new approaches are explained in detail in terms of benefits and disadvantages, thus allowing the college lecturer to use either of these methods or to transform them into his own.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 General Background

In recent years, much work was directed at engineering education research [1-6]. New methodologies were suggested and there was a wide understanding that the classical approach of frontal theoretical lectures on-campus and exercise assignments off-campus must change. Some approaches suggested incorporating distant learning into the curriculum [7-9], this approach was adopted by many academies around the world due to the COVID-19 plague. Other approaches suggested a flipped classroom [10-12] where the students are expected to study the theory off-campus and the on-campus activity should become a more interactive practical discussion with the lecturer, we will elaborate on this approach in the next subsection. Different researchers suggested a combination of distant learning, flipped classroom, project-based learning (PBL) [13-16] and other methodologies in a framework called hybrid-learning or blended-learning [17-19]. In the next section we look closer at the concept of the flipped classroom, try to understand its pros and cons, and establish motivation for novel pedagogies.

1.2 The Flipped Classroom

The flipped classroom was first introduced by Bergmann and Sams in 2012, in the context of high-school chemistry teaching. The concept was later adopted in various degrees of education from kindergarten to academy. One of the possible implementations of the flipped classroom is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model for the flipped classroom teaching method for a single session.

As seen in Figure 1, before the lecturer meets the students, they must read the theoretical material (and perhaps watch clips on the net or prepare some preliminary exercises). Next, the lecturer meets the students on-campus and they discuss the applications of the theory and solve practical problems together, where the lecturer serves as a coach rather than a teacher. After the lecture, the students return home and prepare off-campus assignment (either analytical exercises or practical mini-projects).

This seems like a refreshing change from the somewhat outdated classical pedagogy. However, this is true when addressing a single session. when we observe

two successive sessions along the timeline, as In Figure 2, we begin to see the problem.

Fig. 2. Model for the flipped classroom teaching method for two successive sessions.

In the third step, shown in Figure 2, the students have just finished practicing the previous subject and they must start reading the theory of the following subject without getting a real feedback from the lecturer on the previous work. This way if a student failed to understand a single subject, he/she might be trapped in a loop of not understanding the following subjects, and off-campus feedback might just not be sufficient. Thus, the lack of symmetry between on-campus and off-campus activities might generate a problem. When referring to periphery College students whose ability to face the material alone without guidance is much smaller than that of University students this becomes a huge drawback.

In the next section, the author suggests several alterations to the classical flipped classroom pedagogy in order to adjust it to the periphery College students.

2 NEW PEDAGOGY FOR ACADEMIC COLLEGE ENGINEERING (PACE)

In this section we demonstrate several novel pedagogies that are all related to academic studies in peripheral Engineering Colleges. All the following are adjustments that may be used in other establishments but are most appropriate for teaching a bachelor's degree in engineering in small Colleges in the periphery where most students have slightly lower high-school achievements than those who attend the Universities. We call these methods of teaching (and learning) Pedagogy of Academic College Engineering, or PACE for short.

2.1 The Sine Wave Model

First, one has to correct the un-symmetry of the original flipped classroom model. The College students need more on-campus time with the lecturer to fully understand the material. To do this the author suggests adding an extra on-campus meeting to each session as shown in Figure 3a.

Fig. 3a. The Sine wave model for a single session.

As shown in the model, the off-campus practice is followed by an extra on-campus meeting with the lecturer where he/she discusses the expected outcomes of the off-campus practice and draws a line from the session just finished to the one that will start next, by giving the students motivation and direction before they return home to study the theory of the following session. This way, the students and lecturer discuss issues on assignments and conclude on previous material before the lecturer gives a brief motivation for next subject.

If we look at several successive sessions as in Figure 3b, we can see the resemblance of the model to a Sine wave, giving the model its name.

Fig. 3b. The Sine wave model for two successive sessions.

Unfortunately, reality is not fully symmetric and the time the students need for pre lecture off-campus studies is not equal to the time they need for post lecture off-campus studies; thus, a correction must be made.

2.2 The Sinc Model

The standard classical teaching approach requires 1 hour off-campus for every 1 hour on-campus, original flipped classroom requires 2 hours off-campus for every 1 hour on-campus and the Sine wave model requires 2 hours off-campus for every 2 hours on-campus. However, most College students in the periphery work for a living during the studies and many of them are already raising their own families, so they have less time on their hand. For this reason, a new time-division method must be

used to transfer more activity to the campus without harming the quality of learning. To do this the author suggests to use a slightly non-symmetric approach as shown in figure 4a.

Fig. 4a. The Sinc model for a single session.

As shown in the figure, the timeline is now divided into six nonsymmetric regions. First the lecturer meets the students for a short introduction on the upcoming subjects. Then, the student return home and read (or view) the theoretical background. Next, the lecturer and students meet on campus for a long session divided into two parts. In the first part the lecturer and students discuss the theory and give examples, in the second part the students try to solve various problems that might have been given as home assignments in other circumstances. The lecturer serves as a guide in this sub-session, directing the students rather than telling them the solutions. At the end of the 2nd part the lecturer gives the students guidelines for solving the homework assignments. In the next step, 5th in total, the students solve small scale problems off-campus, and at the final stage the lecturer meets the students for a short session where he/she explains what was expected in the assignments.

When looking at the shape of the model we can see something similar to a Sine over its argument (SA) function, as in Equation 1.

$$SA(x) = \frac{\sin(x)}{x} \quad (1)$$

Since we are talking about engineering students, who prefer to use the Sinc function given in Equation 2, we call this model the Sinc Model.

$$\text{Sinc}(x) = \frac{\sin(\pi x)}{\pi x} \quad (2)$$

In Figure 4b one can see several successive sessions. When looking at several sessions, one can understand that the course must begin with an on-campus short meeting where the lecturer describes the course's syllabus and pedagogy and gives primary motivation before the first off-campus task. One can also notice that not only the two large-scale on-campus meeting can be combined into one extensive meeting, but also the two smaller sub-sessions of Discussion and A-priori data can be combined into one single meeting.

In the Sinc model, most studying is done on-campus, thus the lecturer must use a large percent of the time for small group discussions and problem solving. But what if the lecturer can't divide the class to small groups for discussions and problem solving? E.g., a class of 200 students (very hard to monitor and access all the groups or even to find a lecture hall) or only 2 hours on-campus meeting with students (not enough time for real discussion and deductive reasoning.). In such a case, we need a different approach as depicted in the next subsection.

Fig. 4b. The Sinc model for three successive sessions.

2.3 The Signed-Sinc Model

We are looking for a variation in the model to allow more symmetric time division between on-campus and off-campus activity in case significant part of the practice must be off-campus either offline or online. Since the time required for obtaining theoretical background is expected to be smaller than the time required for post-lecture exercise and since the time required for the lecturer to convert theoretical knowledge to practical knowledge is expected to be larger than the time required for post-lecture discussion, the author suggest the model shown in Figure 5a.

Fig. 5a. The Signed-Sinc model for a single session.

Since the model appears to be similar to the Sinc model with the exception that the right half is the inverse of the left half, we call this a Signed-Sinc model. When considering several successive sessions, we obtain the diagram shown in Figure 5b.

Fig. 5b. The Signed-Sinc model for several successive sessions.

Since the ending of one session is actually the beginning of the following session, Figure 5b can be redrawn as in Figure 5c to demonstrate the flow of the entire course. As shown in the diagram, the first meeting on-campus is used for defining the pedagogy, giving an introduction and a-priori motivation for first subject. During the semester the students build (physically or virtually, depending on the course) a small-scale project, and at the end of each session they can add a new part to that project. The Signed-Sinc model will be presented to the “2021 Innovation in Engineering Education” Forum at the author's College as a preferred option to improve teaching and learning potential.

Fig. 5c. The Signed-Sinc model for several successive sessions.

In all the three suggested models (Sine, Sinc and Signed-Sinc) the curriculum requires a 2 meetings per week scenario (or that each session lasts two weeks). In case were a session lasts only one week and there is only one weekly on-campus meeting we suggest a slightly altered version of the Sinc approach, shown in Figure 5d. in this approach the discussion and motivation are given on-line via Zoom. A summation of all methods suggested in this paper is given in Table 1, as different methodologies might be suitable for different establishments or courses.

Fig. 5d. A revised Sinc model for single weekly on-campus courses.

Table 1. Comparison of PACE models

Pedagogy	Advantages	Disadvantages	Best for...
Classical Flipped Classroom	Meaningful on-campus activity	Requires a lot of self-preparations off-campus	Students that have twice as much time off-campus than on-campus
Sine	Symmetry between on and off campus activity	Pre and post lecture activities are not balanced	Students that need feedback after every home assignment
Sinc	Balanced Pre and post lecture activities	Requires many hours on-campus	Students that have little time off-campus
Signed-Sinc	Balanced Pre and post lecture activities	Requires many hours on-campus	Students that want symmetry between on and off campus activities.
Revised Sinc	Symmetry between Pre and post lecture activities	Discussion and motivation are given via Zoom.	Students that have little time off-campus

3 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the author suggested several new pedagogies for academic teaching, with regards to Engineering Colleges in the periphery. The author described the advantages and disadvantage of each approach in such a manner that every educator may choose the appropriate pedagogy most suitable for their courses. This work is part of the “2021 Innovation in Engineering Education” Forum at the author's College.

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Since we are using double-blind reviewing process, also references revealing the identity of the author(s) should be made anonymous until the final paper.

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